

A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN TUSSAR SILK AND MULBERRY SILK

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Abstract:

Silk is a Natural animal fibre which is extracted from Silk worm. Silk fibre is formed when the larvae spin a double strand of fibre in a figure "8" pattern and constructs a wall around itself. There are several types of silk, of which the major four types are: Mulberry silk, Tussar silk, Eri silk and Muga silk. This research involves a detailed study about Tussar silk and Mulberry silk. The study focuses on the points of unlikeliness between both types of silk. It involves the processes like breeding the silk worm, extracting the fibre, weaving, finishing, etc. It also incorporates the consumer behavior towards both the types of silk fabrics. The survey is carried out in the state of Chhattisgarh. This research highlights the importance of Tussar silk and Mulberry silk among Chhattisgarhi.

Introduction:

Silk has built the standard in luxury fabrics in several decades. The origin of silk goes back to ancient China. A Chinese princess was sipping tea in her garden when a cocoon fell into her cup, and the hot tea loosened the longstrand of silk fibre. Ancient literature symbolizes the popularization of silk to the Chinese Empress Si-Ling, to around 2600 B.C. called the Goddess of the silk worm. Si-Ling apparently raised silk worms and designed a loom for making silk fabrics.

There are four types of natural silk which are commercially known and produced in the world. These important types of silk are Mulberry silk, Tussar silk, Eri silk and Muga silk. In this context we will be focusing on Mulberry silk and Tussar silk.

Manufacturing:

Sericulture is the process of breeding silk worm for commercial purpose. Only the healthiest moths are used for breeding. Their eggs are categorized, graded and tested for infection. The healthiest eggs are placed in cold storage until they are ready to be hatched. Once the eggs are incubated, they usually hatch within 7 days. The mulberry silk worms feed only on the leaves of mulberry plant. The leaves are finely chopped and fed to the silk worms every few hours for 20 to 35 days. The tussar silk worms feed on several trees such as Axle wood, Saaj, Arjun tree and Mahuwa. The size of the worms increases to about 3.5 inches. They shed their skin or molt four times and change colour from gray to a translucent pinkish colour.

The caterpillar attaches itself to a twig or rack for support and twists its head to spin a double strand of fibre in a figure eight pattern and constructs a wall around itself. The insoluble protein-like fibre is called fibroin and is held together by a soluble gum secreted by the worm called sericin. The Seri culturists then destroy the chrysalis so that it does not break the silk filament. This is done by stoving the chrysalis in heat. The cocoons must be soaked in hot water to loosen the sericin. After that, reeling may be done manually or automatically. As each filament is about to get finished, a new fiber is twisted onto it, forming one long continuous thread. Silk thread or yarn is formed by throwing or twisting the reeled raw silk. As the silk filaments are reeled onto bobbins, they are twisted in a manner to form a particular texture of yarn. The silk yarn is put through rollers to make the width more uniform. The yarn is then inspected, weighed, and packaged to send it to fabric manufacturers.

Mulberry Silk:

This type of silk dates to the Indus Valley Civilization. Mulberry silk comes from the silk worm, Bombyx mori which feeds on the mulberry plant. These silk worms are completely reared indoors. India is the second largest producer of silk after China. In India, the major mulberry silk producing states are Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Karnataka, and Jammu & Kashmir.

Mulberry silk is lustrous and gives fall that is desired in every fabric. It is very versatile; right from evening wear to sarees this fabric shows the world a vast taste of designs and apparels. Now, silk is mixed with other textiles and it led to the introduction of various apparels. It has popularized itself as a furnishing fabric too. Many people have silk drapes pulled across their windows or silk covers for their furniture.

The shine and luster of mulberry silk suggests that it should be worn during festivals, parties, or other formal occasions. Silk is suitable for the cold climate, wearing it during rainy season should be avoided as it becomes weak in water and loses its shine and luster.

Tussar Silk:

Tussar silk was discovered during medieval times. There was no trace of silk being made from any other natural or artificial object in place of mulberry fed silk worms. Kosa silk is the Sanskrit name of Tussar

silk. IT is widely known for its natural gold colours, which it gets from Antheriapaphia, Antheriamilita and Antheriaproylei.

Tussar silk is a lot more textured than Mulberry silk and is used in creating Tussar silk sarees and silk suits. Tussarsilk can be easily molded into Indian traditional attires. The dull gold texture that it radiates gives a suitable basefor embroideries as well as print motifs. Floral patterns and tribal prints give attractive surface ornamentation onthe fabric.

Tussar silk is not only limited to traditional wear but also contributes in making of western garments such as Trench coats, Blazers, Waist coats, etc. Due to its stiffness and neutral appeal it is suitable to wear it in formal occasions. The fabric is also cooler than the other varieties of silk and is a lot more porous, therefore, breathable.

Review of Literature:

1. A Study on the Public Aesthetic Perception of Silk Fabrics of Garments

Silk has several excellent qualities, but the perception status of public on property regarding to silk fabrics of garment is not clear. In the paper, four indicators (Gloss, Drapability, Wrinkle resistance and Pilling) were usedto analyze the status of the public aesthetic perception of silk fabrics through questionnaire investigation and statistical analysis based on surveys conducted from the public of Hangzhou, China as core objects.

The result shows that public owns high perception on the Gloss and Drapability of silk fabrics of garment and factors such as gender, personal preference, purchase and use experience, whether the silk industry practitioners are of a significant impact on perception. Most of aesthetic evaluations are based on subjective judgments, but the evaluation method is still a weak spot of garment research till now due to different individual evaluation criteria and clothing preferences (Luo, 2014, p. 46).

The higher the monthly income or education level, the higher the perception. Age and Life span are of no significant impact.

With the improvement of people's living and standards, the demand for garment appearance are getting higher. Silk fabrics have become the first choice of high-grade garments due to its noble, elegant, soft, and flowing property.

2. An Empirical Study of the Preferences and Buying Behavior of Silk Sarees among Women Consumers

Silk, the queen of textiles dominates the textile industry with its luster, sensuousness, and glamour. Today, silk weaving tradition in India revolves around the saree, the ethnic traditional wear that is worn in most parts of the country. The vibrant colour, light weight, resilience and excellent drape have made silk sarees, the irresistible and unavoidable companion of Indian women. Indian silk is popular all over the world with its variety of designs, weaves, and patterns.

The objectives of the study was: To describe the buying behavior of women for silk saree in general, To identifythe preferences towards silk sarees in different brands and in different place of purchase, To study the socio economic characters of the sample respondents and their purchasing pattern of silk sarees. To fulfill the set objective, a sample study was undertaken by using a well-framed questionnaire that was duly filled by the respondents. The secondary pertaining to the study was gathered from the records of major silk saree shops and silk mark society. The factors were studied by means of percentages, Chi-square test, Anova analysis and Henry Garrett ranking technique.

The study has tried to bring out the awareness of 'silk mark' products in Vellore District. This study would certainly help the consumers to become aware of 'natural silk' and 'silk mark' scheme, so that they get pure and genuine silk for the money they spend. This study gives an overall picture that women are lovers of quality dress materials irrespective of their education level and income level. Women are quality conscious, tradition and heritage lovers and hence they have given enough importance to the traditional silk in general.

Research Methodology:

The research focused on the consumer buying behavior towards Mulberry silk and Tussar silk. In this study, the perception of various middle-aged women of the state Chhattisgarh were taken into account. The research was also carried out among the employees of a Kosa manufacturing unit in Jagdalpur city.

The sample of the population of this study includes 50 middle-aged women and 10 employees of Kosa Centre, Jagdalpur. A random sampling technique was used for selecting the participants for this study. A questionnaire was designed as one of the instruments for data collection for the study. There was also an interview with the employees of a Kosa manufacturing unit. The interview comprises of open-end questions. The prepared questionnaire was distributed among the chosen sample for the study. Fifty copies of the questionnaire given were successfully completed and received. The main purpose of this survey was to determine the points of unlikeliness between Tussar Silk and Mulberry silk.

Results and Discussion:

As per the data analysis, there has been several things learned and discovered. The following are the findings during the study:

- Tussar silk is purchased more in short intervals than Mulberry silk.

- When it comes to attending any party, Mulberry silk is preferred over Tussar silk. On the other hand, when work place is considered, Tussar silk is majorly preferred over Mulberry silk.
- In terms of durability, Tussar silk is widely preferred over Mulberry silk.
- In terms of outlook, Tussar silk is preferred over Mulberry silk.
- When comfort is considered, Tussar silk is preferred over Mulberry silk.
- The texture of Tussar silk is found to be better than Mulberry silk.
- The study shows that Mulberry silk has more variety than Tussar silk.
- When drapability is taken into consideration, Tussar silk is better.
- Mulberry silk offers more variety in colour as it can be easily dyed.

Conclusion:

- Tussar silk is purchased more because it is less expensive than Mulberry silk.
- Due to its luster and richness, Mulberry silk is preferred over Tussar silk when it comes to attending any function. Whereas, Tussar silk is neutral it is preferred in the work place.
- Tussar silk is considered durable as it is not a delicate fabric and can be easily maintained.
- Tussar silk is porous and breathable so it is comforting in warmer weather.
- It is considered that Mulberry silk has more variety than Tussar silk in terms of colour, as Mulberry silk can be dyed easily.

References:

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